

ANNEXURE 4.1: Figures

Figures A4.1.1 (A to J): Individual Organism Profiles.

Figure A4.1.1 A: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Homo sapiens* (Animal). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1 B: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Mus musculus* (Animal). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 C: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Rattus norvegicus* (Animal). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 D: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Drosophila melanogaster* (Animal). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1 E: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Animal). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 F: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Plant). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 G: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Zea mays* (Plant). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 H: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Fungi). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 I: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Kluyveromyces lactis* (Fungi). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.1 J: Biophysical profiles of key genomic elements across the *Yarrowia lipolytica* (Fungi). The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters (BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, Solvation) across eight genomic sites, with positions relative to the genomic site set to 0. Panels (A.) to (H.) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A.) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B.) Promoters, (C.) Gene Start, (D.) Gene End, (E.) Exon Start, (F.) Exon End, (G.) Start Codon, and (H.) Stop Codon. The x-axis represents the position relative to the site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. The profiles reveal distinct structural and energetic patterns specific to each genomic element, indicating their critical roles within the organism.

Figure A4.1.2: Comparison of organism Profiles with Kingdom Profile.

Figure A4.1.2.1 (A to H): for Organisms in Animalia (Figure Caption at the bottom of Figure Panel H).

Figure A4.1.2.1: Comparative biophysical profiles across eight genomic sites in organisms under Animalia. The figure displays the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—across various genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) represent different genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. Each subplot within a panel compares the biophysical profiles of five species—*Homo sapiens* (orange), *Mus musculus* (blue), *Rattus norvegicus* (green), *Drosophila melanogaster* (yellow), and *Caenorhabditis elegans* (purple)—against the average profile across all species (grey line). These comparisons highlight both the conserved and species-specific biophysical characteristics at each genomic site, providing insights into the structural and energetic landscapes that define these regions.

Figure A4.1.2.2 (A to H): for Organisms in Plantae (Figure Caption at the bottom of Figure Panel H).

Figure A4.1.2.2: Comparative biophysical profiles across eight genomic sites in organisms under Plantae. The figure displays the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—across various genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) represent different genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. Each subplot within a panel compares the biophysical profiles of two species—*Arabidopsis thaliana* (orange), and *Zea mays* (blue)—against the average profile across all species (grey line). These comparisons highlight both the conserved and species-specific biophysical characteristics at each genomic site, providing insights into the structural and energetic landscapes that define these regions.

Figure A4.1.2.3 (A to H): for Organisms in Fungi (Figure Caption at the bottom of Figure Panel H).

Figure A4.1.2.3: Comparative biophysical profiles across eight genomic sites in organisms under Fungi. The figure displays the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—across various genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) represent different genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. Each subplot within a panel compares the biophysical profiles of two species—*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (orange), *Kluyveromyces lactis* (blue), and *Yarrowia lipolytica* (green)—against the average profile across all species (grey line). These comparisons highlight both the conserved and species-specific biophysical characteristics at each genomic site, providing insights into the structural and energetic landscapes that define these regions.

Figure 4.1.3 (A to N): Correlation Plots For Kingdoms

Figure A4.1.3 A: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in Animalia. The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the kingdom.

Figure A4.1.3 B: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in Plantae. The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the kingdom.

Figure A4.1.3 C: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in Fungi. The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the kingdom.

Figure A4.1.3 D: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in Protista (*Plasmodium falciparum*). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the kingdom.

For organisms

Organisms under Animalia

Figure A4.1.3 E: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Homo sapiens* (Animal). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 F: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Mus musculus* (Animal). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 G: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Rattus norvegicus* (Animal). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 H: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Drosophila melanogaster* (Animal). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 I: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Animal). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Organisms under Plantae

Figure A4.1.3 J: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Plant). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 K: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Zea mays* (Plant). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Organisms under Fungi

Figure A4.1.3 L: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Fungi). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 M: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Kluyveromyces lactis* (Fungi). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.3 N: Correlation heatmaps of biophysical parameters across eight genomic sites in *Yarrowia lipolytica* (Fungi). The heatmaps display the pairwise correlations between seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—at different genomic sites. Panels (A) through (H) correspond to the following genomic sites: (A) Coding Sequences (CDS), (B) Promoters, (C) Gene Start, (D) Gene End, (E) Exon Start, (F) Exon End, (G) Start Codon, and (H) Stop Codon. The color gradient indicates the strength and direction of correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue representing negative correlations. These plots reveal the intricate relationships between structural and energy parameters at each genomic site, highlighting both conserved and site-specific biophysical interactions within the organism.

Figure A4.1.4 (A to D): PCA-based Clustering Plots.

Figure A4.1.4 A: PCA of biophysical profiles across human genomic elements. The 3D plot shows the separation of seven genomic elements—Promoters, Gene Start, Gene End, Exon Start, Exon End, Start Codon, and Stop Codon—based on their structural and energy parameters across organisms belonging to Animalia: *Homo sapiens* (circles), *Mus musculus* (triangles), *Rattus norvegicus* (squares), *Drosophila melanogaster* (stars), and *Caenorhabditis elegans* (plus). The axes represent the first three PCs (PC1, PC2, and PC3), which together account for 88.44% of the variance.

Figure A4.1.4 B: PCA of biophysical profiles across plant genomic elements. The 3D plot shows the separation of seven genomic elements—Promoters, Gene Start, Gene End, Exon Start, Exon End, Start Codon, and Stop Codon—based on their structural and energy parameters across organisms belonging to Plantae: *Arabidopsis thaliana* (circles), and *Zea mays* (triangles). The axes represent the first three PCs (PC1, PC2, and PC3), which together account for 92.33% of the variance.

Figure A4.1.4 C: PCA of biophysical profiles across Fungi genomic elements. The 3D plot shows the separation of seven genomic elements—Promoters, Gene Start, Gene End, Exon Start, Exon End, Start Codon, and Stop Codon—based on their structural and energy parameters across organisms belonging to Fungi: *Kluyveromyces lactis* (circles), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (triangles), and *Yarrowia lipolytica* (squares). The axes represent the first three PCs (PC1, PC2, and PC3), which together account for 86.28% of the variance.

Figure A4.1.4 D: PCA of biophysical profiles across Protist genomic elements. The 3D plot shows the separation of seven genomic elements—Promoters, Gene Start, Gene End, Exon Start, Exon End, Start Codon, and Stop Codon—based on their structural and energy parameters across a single Protist: *Plasmodium falciparum* (circles). The axes represent the first three PCs (PC1, PC2, and PC3), which together account for 98.03% of the variance.

Figure A4.1.5: Energy and Structure profiles in Humans at Enhancer Start/End, 5' UTR Start/End, and 3' UTR Start/End.

Figure A4.1.5: Biophysical profiles of human Enhancers and UTRs. The plots display the normalized values of seven biophysical parameters—BP-axis, Inter, Intra, Backbone, H-bond, Stacking, and Solvation—across the six different genomic sites in the human genome. Panels (A.) through (F.) correspond to the genomic sites: (A.) Enhancer Start, (B.) Enhancer End, (C.) 5' UTR Start, (D.) 5' UTR End, (E.) 3' UTR Start, and (F.) 3' UTR End. The x-axis represents the position relative to the genomic site, and the y-axis represents the normalized biophysical values. These profiles reveal unique biophysical landscapes that characterize these regulatory regions in the human genome.